

IR26 (SC26), which damaged IR26 and Mudgo, was evaluated in seedling bulk and survival rate tests, with the original Gaozhou BPH colony as control. The varieties responded differently to the populations in the seedling bulk test (Fig. 1). TN1 showed susceptibility to the original Gaozhou BPH, IR26 was moderately resistant, and Mudgo, ASD7, IR36, and IR56 were resistant. TN1, IR26, and Mudgo were susceptible to the newly isolated SC26 population, IR36 was

moderately resistant, and ASD7 and IR56 were resistant. The survival of the SC26 population on varieties differed: survival on IR26 and TN1 was significantly higher than on Mudgo, IR36, ASD7, and IR56 (Fig. 2).

Although BPH biotype 1 was dominant in the Gaozhou colony, some BPH biotype 2 insects were found. IR26 could be damaged by BPH biotype 2; mature Mudgo plants could not. □

Wild rice: a new host for *Hysteronura setariae* (Thomas) [Hemiptera: Aphididae] in the Philippines

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The rusty plum aphid *H. setariae*, a vector of sugarcane and soybean mosaic virus, is a polyphagous pest that occurs yearround in coconut, coffee, and grasses [particularly *Echinochloa* spp., *Leptochloa chinensis* (L.) Nees, and

Eleusine indica (L.) Gaertn.] and occasionally in wheat and rice.

The wingless female is dark brown, shiny, and relatively small (1.70 mm long, 1.00 mm wide), with black antennal segments 1 and 2 and apices of segments 5 and 6, black siphunculi long and cylindrical, cauda white and parallel-sided. The frontal tubercles in the head are absent. The winged form is 1.50 mm long and 0.70 mm wide with a dark brown head and thorax. The forewing has a twice-forked median vein and the hindwing has a cubitus (Fig. 1).

For the last 5 yr, *H. setariae* has invaded wild rices *Oryza minuta* Presley and *O. officinalis* Wall in an IIRRI greenhouse. Aphid density was high (>50 aphids or 2-6 colonies/panicle) during the Jan-Apr dry season, but no yield loss has been reported.

We studied the effect of aphid feeding at different densities on grain development. Each booting tiller was enclosed in a 2.5- × 11-in cylindrical mylar cage with

a nylon mesh vent on top and a sleeve on the side. Aphids were released into cages at six densities, and the sleeve was taped to prevent escape. *H. setariae* were allowed to feed on the panicle for 96 h and then were killed by a pyrethroid insecticide. Percent of damaged grain was determined using the formula

$$\% \text{ damage (adjusted)} = \frac{U(\%) - u(\%)}{100 - u(\%)} \times 100$$

where U is percent unfilled grains in each test and u the percent unfilled grains in the control.

Aphid feeding produced 4-43% empty grains, proportional to pest density (Fig. 2). The relatively low fertility of wild rices, particularly *O. officinalis*, was further reduced by aphid feeding. *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis* appear to have little or moderate resistance to aphids. □

Comparing parasitoid-host responses in laboratory experiments

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Parasitoid-host responses are determined in the laboratory by recording host parasitization at different parasitoid densities. Two components of the functional response are estimated: instantaneous attack rate *a* and a satiation factor, or handling time T_h .

One way to obtain these estimates is with nonlinear curve-fitting procedures found in statistical packages such as SAS, BMDP, and MINITAB. While these methods often provide standard errors of the parameter estimates from which comparisons can be made, they generally do not permit comparisons of the curve of total responses.

In a statistical test for significance between two or more functional response curves, two assumptions are inherent: 1) a null hypothesis that the curves represent samples from a common population, and 2) that the best possible sets of parameters describing the model's function can be estimated.

The parasitoid-host functional

1. Winged form of the female *H. setariae*.

2. Correlation of different aphid densities per panicle with damaged grain in wild rices *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis*.

responses are well described by the Random Parasitoid Equation and are characterized by the parameters a and T_h . Thus, the respective curves may be compared to the curve obtained using pooled data.

We used two simple statistical methods to compare the response curves of the parasitoid *Cardiochiles philippinensis* attacking larvae of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. In the F -test, the residual sums of squares (RSS) of each separate curve were totaled and compared with the RSS of the pooled curve (see table).

In the nonparametric rank-sums test, a single functional response curve was fitted to the pooled data, and residuals computed. The residuals for each sample

Parameter estimates (\pm asymptotic SEs) of the Random Parasitoid Equation of *Cardiochiles philippinensis* attack at different larval stages of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

Larval instar	a	T_h	RSS ^a	CV (%)
Second	1.53 \pm 1.29	0.60 \pm 0.09	46.56	76.8
Third	2.81 \pm 1.75	0.28 \pm 0.03	50.83	43.9
Fourth	7.11 \pm 15.85	0.55 \pm 0.06	37.98	57.9
Pooled	2.32 \pm 1.16	0.43 \pm 0.03	178.36	64.0

^aRSS = residual sum of squares.

Functional responses of the larval parasitoid *Cardiochiles philippinensis* attacking second-, third-, and fourth-larval instars of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. Means (\square) are presented with SEs at 95% confidence level. The curves are generated using a and T_h estimates from the table.

were arranged in a single array, largest negative to largest positive, using PROC NPARIWAY available in SAS.

The figure shows the functional responses. The rank-sums test was highly significant ($P_{RS} = 0.0001$); the F -test was more conservative ($0.05 < P_F < 0.01$). The curve differences were primarily due to

different handling times. T_h for the third instar was 0.28, significantly lower than for the second and fourth instars (see table).

The rank-sums test does not assume normal distribution of the data and is thus a more appropriate test. \square

Co-variation between insects in a ricefield and important spider species

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Spiders are among the first arthropods to colonize wetland rice. Most common are *Pardosa* (= *Lycosa*) *pseudoannulata*, *Atypena* (= *Callitrichia*) *formosana*, and *Tetragnatha* *maxillosa*. These spiders are polyphagous predators that feed on the adults and nymphs of many insect species. The presence of spiders might influence the establishment and increase of pest populations.

We collected arthropods from an IIRRI plot at weekly intervals using an insect suction machine (FARMCOP). All species were identified and counted. The data on rice hoppers and dipterans collected during the cropping period were

linearly regressed with number of important spider species.

T. maxillosa populations appeared to be directly related to number of dipterans, suggesting a positive numerical response (see table). Similar relationships were found between *A. formosana* and BPH, WBPH, dipterans, and all hoppers.

P. pseudoannulata populations, however, were not related to BPH and WBPH.

The differences in the relationships of the three spider species to rice arthropods may be a result of different predatory habits. *T. maxillosa* is a horizontal orb-web building spider that tends to catch more flying insects. \square

Regression analysis of linear relationships between insects and spiders in ricefields. ^a IIRRI 1989.

Insects	<i>T. maxillosa</i>			<i>A. formosana</i>			<i>P. pseudoannulata</i>		
	a	b	F value	a	b	F value	a	b	F value
BPH	0.345	0.001	0.003 ns	1.152	0.174	10.970**	4.662	0.038	0.114 ns
WBPH	0.331	0.012	0.103 ns	1.221	0.143	4.041 *	4.082	-0.091	0.368 ns
GLH	0.261	0.019	2.373 ns	1.263	0.033	2.083 ns	3.997	0.153	10.218 **
Dipterans	0.146	0.268	16.348 **	1.604	-0.255	4.028 *	4.083	0.311	9.055 **
Total hoppers	0.192	0.021	3.152 ns	0.856	0.076	12.356 **	3.678	0.137	8.872 **
Totalinsects	0.019	0.011	3.047 ns	0.933	0.060	8.754 **	3.520	0.144	11.722 **

^aa = intercept, b = slope, ns = not significant, * = significant at $P < 0.05$, ** = significant at $P < 0.01$.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.